

CRITICAL CONTRIBUTIONS OF LEADERSHIP AND MANAGEMENT IN ACHIEVING ORGANISATIONAL EFFECTIVENESS

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Abstract:

The purpose of this study was to provide a comprehensive analysis on the critical contributions of leadership and management to organizational effectiveness. The researcher used purposive sampling. The study used primary and secondary data. Primary data were transcriptions of respondents from face to face interview and focused group discussion. Data were analyzed in a descriptive framework using content analytical technique. The eight critical contributions of leadership identified were developing vision and setting direction, collaboration through trust, inspiration for innovation, opportunity for initiative and creativity, influence as major incentive, greater opportunity for learning, genuine care for worker wellbeing, and building harmonious and agile organization. The eight critical contributions of management identified were provision of manpower skills and material resource, developing annual objective and strategy, greater opportunity for a continuous professional development, developing code of ethics, supervision of workforce and material resources, supervision of implementation of policies and strategies, reward as incentive and effective appraisal strategy. Majority of respondents shared the view that in the 21st century equal proportion and amalgamation of both leadership and management functions is needed to make organizations effective.

Key Words: Leadership and Management, Organisational Effectiveness

Introduction:

Leadership and management are broadly stimulating and profound discourse within the business environment because the concepts of management and leadership are synonymous in their use. Though leadership and management may have separate functions, their implications for business organisations cannot be under estimated. Within literature and business environment many scholars have alluded to both business failure and success to leadership and management in terms of their critical contributions and competencies. The appropriate understanding of the similarities, differences and critical contributions of the functions of leadership and management by business executives influence organisational effectiveness. This paper seeks to analyse critical contributions of leadership and management to organisational effectiveness.

Review of Literature:

Leadership involves processes leaders and followers engage in to initiate change (Laub, 2004). This definition considers the end result of leadership which is change. He argues that leadership processes are meant to create change. On the other hand, Stodgill shares the view that leadership has to do with influencing the activities of an organized group in its efforts toward goal setting and goal achievement (Stodgill, 1950). Unlike Laub, Stodgill highlights the influencing of organized group in order to achieve goals of an organisation. Stodgill concentrates on leadership as a goal setting and goal achievements. Leadership is the behavior of an individual when he is directing the activities of a group toward shared goal (Hemphill, 1957).

On the other hand, the concept of management has variants definitions and this is due to how different scholars see it in relations to environment, context, purpose and time. Olum (2004) sees management as the art or science of achieving goals through people. Olum considers management as managers making sure people do what they are supposed to do to enhance productivity and continuous improvements. Management promotes the achievement of goal through people. On the other hand, Koontz and Wehrich (1990) share the view that management is the process of designing and maintaining an environment in which individuals, working together in group efficiently accomplish selected aims.

John P. Kotter's Perspective on Leadership Functions versus Management Functions:

Kotter (1990: 25:30) identifies management as a set of process that keeps complicated systems of people and technology smoothly focusing mainly on planning, organizing and controlling work force. Kotter (1990: 25-30) in contrast refers to leadership as a set of process that create organisation and adapts them to significantly changing circumstances. Kotter in his assessment of the two concepts agrees that both involve a set of processes and these processes in the leadership and management process lead to something different. Leadership process creates an adjustable organisation based on prevailing circumstance however management

processes ensure complicated systems of organisation run smoothly without any impediment. Kotter (1990) asserts five leadership functions that make it different from management.

Structures and cultures are a basic differentiator of leadership roles from management roles. Kotter in his definition of the two concepts indicates that management deals with formal structures and decision making. On the other hand, leadership roles deal with creating a culture that significantly produces the best out of prevailing circumstance. Leadership role embraces transformational process for organisational effectiveness. Though management process focuses on culture, leadership process focuses on culture as reinforcement.

Aligning and organizing as a differentiator of leadership and management functions. Alignment deals with correct positioning of people in an organisation in such a way that the efforts of the work force will be beneficial to organisational effectiveness. Alignment of people covers employment, motivation and many more than just organizing which only has to do with creating human systems that accomplish plans effectively. The systems in the organizing process cover determining structures and reporting relationships that can determine proper accountability depending on the staffing, training, execution of responsibilities, monitoring and controlling systems.

Handling complex situation and change is a differentiating factor of leadership roles from management roles. In the situation of uncertainty happening management functions has to do with coping with complexities in order to exist. Coping with complexities, management would have to go through restructuring and designing systems that responds to the competition. However, Kotter asserts that leadership in times of turbulence has to do with rescinding change by altering the behaviors of workers for maximum performance. This is done through motivation inspiration and encouraging the heart of subordinates. Leadership is therefore influencing the behaviors of subordinate to adequately respond to change while management has to do with restructuring of organisational systems to respond to change.

Creating value for business differentiate leadership roles from management roles. Kotter believes that to create values for business leadership set vision and direction for the future. This is done through establishing clear strategies to be followed by the entire organisation to achieve the vision. However, management deals with complex situation by going through progress of planning, organizing and budgeting. This is done by setting targets for subordinate to achieve within a period of time whether short, medium or long term. Kotter provides a clear difference of both leadership and management in terms of creating value for businesses because setting direction in leadership and planning in management is a two set of roles. Setting direction creates a vision and strategy for an organisational effectiveness. However, planning is done to achieve results in a systematic order depending on structures and budgeting of the organisation.

Motivation and inspiration differentiate leadership functions from management functions. Kotter posits that leadership is able to produce highly motivated and inspired people to raise their energies for higher performance. On the other hand, because management process deals with planning, controlling and directing it does not produce extraordinary people with the needed motivation and energy for organisational effectiveness. It is therefore clear that to generate a good change in organisation it depends on a motivated, inspired workforce who have the right energy to negotiate barriers that can impede organisational effectiveness.

Joseph C. Rost Perspective on Leadership Functions versus Management Functions:

Rost (1993, p. 149) suggests that leadership is an influence relationship between leaders and followers intended for real changes which reflects on mutual purposes. On the other hand, Rost (1993) indicates that management is an authority relationship between managers and subordinate coordinated to produce goods and service. Unlike Kotter (1990) who sees leadership and management as set of processes, Rost (1993) sees both concept as relationship based to achieve certain results, Rost indicates that relationship is an important distinction or differentiator between leadership functions and management functions. Leadership deals with influencing subordinates for achievement of set goals. This influence relationship is multidimensional where the leader influences the followers and vice-versa. On the other hand, management as authority relationship makes use of coercion to get subordinates for higher performance. This is done by the establishment of formal structures, reporting and accountability lines. Leadership may use inspiration and motivation to influence relationship but management use command system to establish authority relationship.

Position of authority is a differentiator of leadership roles from management roles. Rost (1993) asserts that leaders and followers versus managers and subordinates are not the same. Both followers and managers can be managers but leaders are not necessarily managers. Rost identifies that leadership does not mean a position of power or authority rather it is provided in all levels of the organisational structure but management establishes a clear accountability and authority systems from organisational authority systems from organisational hierarchy. This means that leadership is multidimensional whilst management is unidimensional. Rost's (1993) distinction between leadership and management is not comprehensive enough unlike Kotter's who establishes a comprehensive literature on the distinction between the two concepts though both scholars highlight extensively on relationship as a major distinction between leadership and management functions.

Northouse' Perspective on Leadership Functions versus Management Functions:

Leadership is a process, a responsibility, an experience, function of management and influencing relationship and ability (Northouse, 2007). However, management is a process by which definite set of objectives are achieved through efficient use of resources (Northouse, 2007). Northouse establishes a clear dichotomy between leadership and management using functions. He indicates that while leadership establishes directions, management deals with planning and budgeting. Leadership creates vision and clarifies the big picture for followers to work toward but management establishes agenda by setting out timelines for job completion and reporting. In terms of people, leadership aligns people but management deals with organizing and safety. Leadership achieves goals by communicating to followers the need for achievement; however, management provides structures that facilitate goal achievement. Building teams and coalitions for organisational effectiveness is a leadership function while management establishes rules and procedures as guiding principles for organisational operations. As leadership motivate and inspires to energize and empower followers in order to satisfying unmet needs for higher performance, management makes use of controlling, developing incentive by generating creative solutions for taking corrective action. Northouse (2007) assertion of leadership and managements agrees with others like Kotter (1990), Rost (1993) and Lunenburg (2011).

The Relevant Proportions of Leadership Functions and Management Functions Needed in Organisational Effectiveness:

Effective organisation ensures the optimal application of leadership and management functions. Algahtani (2014) juxtaposes that it is vital to balance the functions of management and the functions of leadership to ensure the best outcome for organisations. Effective organisations use leadership and management functions as a complementary to each another to achieve goals. Covey (2004) advances a notion that leadership and management functions are very important for organisations that want to thrive in challenging times to gain customer loyalty and competitive advantage. Covey's view advocates equal proportionate use of the two concepts. To support the view of Covey (2004) on the proportionate use of both leadership and management functions in thriving organisations, Kotterman (2006) advocates for strong leadership and strong management. Kotterman's assertion implies an equal optimal utilization of the two concepts. Mabhudhu (2008: 113) asserts that there is a symbiotic relationship between the two functions of management and leadership that create the long lasting value of organisation. The absence of correct proportion is what causes the failure of organisation. Mabhudhu (2008:113) remarks "too much or too little of either is toxic to organisations"

Research methodology:

The research design for the study was a survey using qualitative approach. The study considered leadership and management in twenty five selected private basic educational institutions capturing the knowledge gap of the critical contributions of leadership and management. The researcher used proportionate stratified sampling to select twenty five private basic schools from the sixteen education directorate in the Accra Metropolis and purposive sampling was used for selecting the one hundred (100) school administrators. The study used extensively primary and secondary data. Primary data were transcriptions of respondents from the face to face interview and the focused group discussions. Secondary data included documentary material in and out of the educational institutions. Data were analyzed in a descriptive framework using content analytical technique and descriptive statistics.

Empirical Results:

Critical Contributions of Leadership Function in Organisational Effectiveness:

Leadership contributes critically to the effectiveness of organisations by developing a vision and setting direction for progress of which all members are aligned to make tangible inputs for the realization of the vision even in turbulence times when changes are relevant. Interviewee 88 highlighted that fact:

"Leadership sees the need to move from one place to another when there is the need for change in vision and mission and the connection between the leader and followers indicate a common purpose that relates to motivation for vision achievement though in the long term"

It is leadership that sees how to navigate organisations in perilous times for profitability and effectiveness. This is done collectively by the leader and followers motivated by sense of vision achievement though may be long term. Motivation is imperative in the leadership process in the sense that it gives team members the drive to press on even in the face of hopelessness in order to achieve something worthwhile. The understanding of the vision and possible alterations of it gives the motivation for a collective effort between a leader and the followers.

Collaboration through trust, innovation and inspiration is a critical contributor of leadership functions in organisational effectiveness. Leadership promotes the collaboration of efforts of team members as a united force behind vision and set of directions. This collaboration is achievable through trust and inspiration in an open climate of innovation. The trust between the leader and followers allow innovative efforts to take place. The interaction between the leader and followers goes in light of the behavioral theory where organisational leadership behaviors correlate to the emotional atmosphere of the work force.

“Leader provides the inspiration and trust from followers ... challenges them to be innovative to facilitate the achievement of organisational objectives. (Interviewee 70)

It is leadership that challenges and promotes innovation in organisations. This is so because the collaborative efforts of team members lead to mutual trust of which team members would want to genuinely contribute their quota for organisational effectiveness. The innovation opportunity is what brings on board new ways of doing things in an effective and efficient manner. Without inspiration and trust it becomes difficult to accept the input of other people. However, since leadership creates mutual trust with team members, there is free expression of innovative skills and those who are highly endowed with innovative abilities impact the less endowed.

Greater opportunity for initiative and creativity is a critical contributor of leadership. Leadership contributes to organisations effectiveness by providing opportunity for initiation and creativity. The link between leaders and followers propel followers to initiate agenda capable of aiding the achievement of organisational objectives. The initiation strategy enhances creative abilities on how to make things work out. Creativity submerges primitivism to bring out organisational profitability.

“As for leadership, it allows workers to have the freedom to exercise their responsibility ... It promotes initiative and creativity” (Interviewee 47)

Leadership functions give room for followers to freely perform their responsibility with the sense of initiation and creativity. The space given by a leader propels team members to develop the skills and abilities of initiation and creativity. The creativity of workers serves as the blood line of an organisation. This is supported by Kotter (1990) that leadership creates adjustable organisation depending on prevailing conditions. Conditions of business underpin the creative potentials of workers. Creativity gives life to organisation as better ways of thinking and doing things comes to light. This in the long term leads to effectiveness coupled with available resources to achieve organisational goals and objectives. Creativity and initiation aid in resource utilization, effective use of human efforts and equipment. Followers discharging duties and responsibilities in an environment of creativity enhance organisational effectiveness.

Influence as a major incentive for performance is a critical contributor of leadership function. The theme of influence was largely raised by most respondents. Leadership has influence as a major incentive that drives followers or team members for higher performance. The leadership level of influence propels team members to a higher level of dedication and commitment. Interviewee 31 indicated that:

“You see!!! leadership in itself is a major incentive to organisational growth”

The leader influences by way of example performance, inspiration and guidance motivating followers to give out their best in order to drive the growth of organisation. The influence may come in many forms depending on working environment, team member characteristics, authenticity of leaders influence among others. As Interviewee 31 asserts, the growth of organisations depend on how leadership intuitively and continuously influence subordinate in line of dedication and commitment for facilitating the achievement of goals and objectives. The influence which serves as incentive brings about sense of urgency and eagerness to see the realization of organisational objectives.

Interviewee 13 asserts that “Leadership brings about urgency and eagerness in an organisational strategy to achieve it vision”

With influence as incentive, team members develop the sense of alacrity and desire to accomplish a set objective for the common good of the team. Sense of urgency gives the drive to break through barriers of progress and to navigate challenges capable of impeding on the progress of organisations.

Greater opportunity for learning and grooming is a critical contributor of leadership function in organisational effectiveness. Leadership function provides the opportunity for learning for both the leader and followers. The leader though at the top learns from the followers while the followers are also impacted by the influence, knowledge and skills of the leader. In the leadership process there is a mutual relationship which is reciprocal in nature. One school administrator who believes to discharge leadership roles highlighted that:

“As a leader, I learn from my teachers and they also learn from me we share ideas and put the best together to get things done”

Leadership functions open the doors for learning to take place and for the betterment of team members. The reciprocal learning atmosphere enhances brainstorming, collaboration, sense of belongingness and importance in each team member which in the end affect their productivity and performance positively. Learning from each other among team members promote synergic environment for unusual cooperation and performance.

Genuine care for worker wellbeing is a critical contributor of leadership function in organisational effectiveness. Leadership function affords organisations proper care and guidance for workers as the objectives of the individual worker is aligned to that of organisation. Leadership ensures that the interests of workers are fused into the overall agenda of the organisation. This promotes proper formulation of policies that take care of the wellbeing of workers or team members. Leadership functions bring organisational objectives and personal

goals of team members into equilibrium. In this sense team members work assiduously for the growth of organisation. The individual worker grows along the growth of organisation. Interviewee 11 asserted that:

“Leadership looks at the wellbeing of the workers and students because apart from other resources, the workers and students of every school is key to the sustainability of that school”

Leadership sees workers or team members as a force to reckon with and therefore becomes very imperative to ensure their happiness so that their commitment and dedication to productivity can be pledged to the organisation. Leadership functions of proper care for workers empower organisations effectiveness.

Leadership functions contribute to setting direction for organisational progress regularly in organisational effectiveness. Setting and altering direction and agenda for growth in the leadership function is crucial for proper utilization of human effort. As leadership set direction and agenda, mobilization of human effort comes to the fore as team members become a united force behind the agenda.

Interviewee 5 acknowledged:

“.....leadership determines the direction of the organisation through the demonstration of vision and mission of the school.....”

The setting of agenda comes from the development of vision and mission. Leadership ensures the clearer understanding of the vision to be achieved by followers or team members. This informs the behavior and attitude of team members in terms of urgency and eagerness. Setting the agenda helps members to toll the line of progress and careful to observe all the necessary structures relevant to the achievement of the goals set by an organisation. Leadership agenda contributes to the overall perception of team members concerning the progress of organisation. Setting direction is done for organisations to navigate, mitigate, and conquer all challenges possible to affect the agility of the organisation.

Leadership functions contribute to harmonious and agile organisation. Leadership uses influence and inspiration to get the commitment of workers in the freedom to exercise initiative and creativity. This contributes immensely to organisations agility and harmony. Harmonious organisations stand better chance of progress and higher productivity. The equal playing grounds for both leader and team members enhance peaceful coexistence and sense of responsibility. Interviewee 22 posited:

“Leadership encourages harmonies organisation promoting a sense of responsibility among team member ...”

Leadership of organisations in the process of functioning creates a climate conducive for team members to feel secure and that alone brings the commitment and desire for hard work which in the end lead to higher productivity and organisation wellbeing. The harmony is based on trust between the team members through the influence of the leader.

Critical Contributions of Management Functions to Organisational Effectiveness:

“Management is making available resource and skills needed for implementation of organisation’s strategy and policies to achieve a desired progress” (Interviewee 20)

The above description highlights the relevance and the contributions of management functions in organisational effectiveness.

Management functions contribute to organisational resources and manpower skills. Management of organisations is duty bound to provide the necessary resources and skills needed in carrying out business operations underpinning the relevance of the administrative management theory (Fayol, 1925) where organisations create structures to provide material and human resource to power organisational effectiveness. Qualified personnel are recruited to fit specific job description. The relevant equipment and resources are then given to the workforce to implement the strategies of the organisation. Skillful workers and availability of resource help in the quick implementation of organisations strategy to achieve profitability. Interviewee 65 indicated:

“Management organizes resources and skill to motivate the easy achievement of progress”

Skills and resources serve as motivating factor that facilitates the easy implementation of business strategy. Therefore, workforce may demand different skills at different times in order to meet the demands of an organisation. Where an organisation lacks the needed skills in business operations, it may impede on the progress of the organisation. The supply of resources in right quantity and at the right time leads to effectiveness and profitability. From the assertion of Interviewee 65, human skill is of much prominence to management.

Management functions contribute to the development of annual objectives and strategy. Annual objectives and strategies are developed by management to give direction to operations of organisation. The objectives and strategies may emanate from the overall goal of an organisation divided into short, medium and long term. This is done not only to give direction of operations but also to ignite the sense of responsibility on the side of superiors and subordinates. The objective brings also the sense of urgency of achievement where management makes available resources and skills for strategy implementation.

“Management first of all develops annual objective and strategies and make resources available to achieve the set goals” (Interviewee 50)

Though management must develop strategy and objectives, that is not enough until resources and skills are aligned and committed to the achievement of the target. This means managements coordinate both strategies and resources for organisational effectiveness.

Management functions contribute to greater opportunity for continuous professional development. Management of organisations ensure that workforce are empowered with new knowledge, abilities and skills needed to facilitate growth and expansion. The global changes in technology, business operation systems demand a workforce capable enough to position organisations competitively.

“Management team ensures that there is adequate technical know-how acquired through continuous development program... to run day to day administrative and operational duties of the school” (Interviewee 91) The operational and administrative functions of organisation need teams that have adequate skills necessary to achieve organisation’s goals and objectives. Continuous professional development helps organisational workforce to determine new direction of business operations. Outmoded knowledge, abilities, skills is likely to impede on the progress of organisations. It is clear from Interviewee 91’s assertion that management is duty bound to provide necessary assistance to work force in order to ensure “day to day operational and administrative functions” to propel organisational effectiveness.

Management functions contribute to harmonious organisation using code of ethics. Management team develops code of conduct and ethical standards to promote harmonious organisation so as to reduce organisational conflict. Established ethical standard guides and checks the attitude, character and conflict of interest situation likely to hamper organisational growth and effectiveness.

“...eiiiiii!! management encourages harmonious school environment.....rules and regulations are coded to indicate the level of power of each workerwe all operate in a limited framework just for sense of responsibility and tranquility” (Interviewee 44)

The entire workforce of organisations is regulated by established behavioral principles to mitigate overlap of responsibilities and conflict for peaceful coexistence. This makes organisation effective as each employee discharge described responsibilities by the guidance of rules and regulation. Interviewee 6 emphasized:

“Management assigns tasks and maintains the compliance of work structures and systems” The compliance to work schedules is aided by established standards and violations of the standard may attract certain level of punishment or query.

Management functions contribute to the effective utilization of human and materials resource. Management team importantly aligns resources and human capital to set objective. The next action is to monitor and evaluate the proper utilization of the aligned materials and human resources to control the overhead cost of business operations. There is adequate interaction between human resource and material resource. Kahn and James (1960) highlighted that the system management theory ensure the interaction of various factors of organisation to ensure effectiveness.

“I am part of the management team and what we do is that we provide resources, supervise the use of the resources because all these things I am saying, is done with money..... I must see how the spent of money expands my school ... make profit” (Interviewee 11)

The supervision of the use of resources is important to organisations as the goal of most institutions is to achieve profitability and effectiveness. Lack of effective supervision of supplied resource can cause the progress and expansion of organisation. It then calls for management with necessary ability to control, monitor and evaluate the effective use of resources though may be limited, to achieve organisational goals and objectives. This claim is supported by Interviewee 22: “.... the management team does not only draw policies we monitor the use of things to ensure things are done according to plan”

Management functions contribute to effective implementation of policies and strategies. Organisation management team draws policies and strategies and ensures it effective implementation to achieve organisational goals with a dedicated workforce with requisite experience and knowledge. Management set the standard of implementation with the supply of necessary resources. Schedules of implementation become relevant to aid proper control and monitoring of various faces of activities.

“.....my school management draw, review policies and implement them... dividing work into manageable activities and assign these to relevant head teachers of the various department ... and determine how best to meet those goals” (Interviewee 86)

To implement policies and strategies effectively, management divide work activities and assign them to individuals with relevant knowledge and skills and determine how best to do things to facilitate the overall objective of an organisation.

Management functions use reward as incentive to induce higher performance. Reward system is a major incentive use by management team to facilitate commitment and dedication. Reward induces higher performance for higher productivity. In the management process, job descriptions are attached to reward systems as a motivator. The relationship between job schedule and reward becomes transactional principle where the well appraised gets a reward.

“Myself and others provide information on the job to be done motivate my teachers through good salaries and allowances, bonuses, surprise gifts to get them to do their best to bring my school good fortunes ... I tell them to build it so that we enjoy together” (Interviewee 20). Management gets subordinates to do their best through reward systems. This provides the senses of belongingness and ownership to individual workers. Employees through reward systems work as though they own the business. It helps to avoid labor turnover and enhance job security. The motivation of workers inculcate work attitude of commitment which promotes organisational effectiveness.

Management functions contribute to effective and efficient performance appraisal strategy. Management of organisations does not only align human skills behind the organisation objectives but ensures the effective monitoring and evaluation of performance of the workforce. This is done to facilitate the progress of business operations and when necessary put corrective measures in place (Interviewee 51 Indicated).

“as things are done I measure the work performance of my staff members to mirror the goals of the schoolbecause I supervise their performance I know those who are working hard and those who are not”. The effective appraisal of work identifies and categorizes employees into those contributing their quota towards the achievement of business goals and those who are not. The measurement of performance helps to reorganizes expertise and to influence organisational effectiveness. Through the appraisal strategy of management, employee efforts are equitable distributed across the functional areas of organisations. Interviewee 15 juxtaposed:

“The management team ensures that there is adequate technical know-how..... teaching efforts are equitably disbursed in the organisation”

Management contributes to the strict adherence to organisational systems and structures. The management bureaucratic theory as opined by Webber (1920) indicates that formal systems of organisations and administration are designed to ensure effective and effective organisation. Management of organisation supervises the strict adherence of systems and structures laid down in an organisation. Systems and structures provide guiding principles of business operations leading to organisational effectiveness. The procedural systems and structure avoid conflict mismanagement and better division of labor.

“..... we have systems and structures here that we follow. If you are a teacher here you can't do things anyhow; you must follow the systems...everyone does his part as a team member. I am manager so I check to see to it that all my teachers do what is expected of them following the laid down system and structure” (Interviewee 33)

The concern of management is to ensure that the work force follow systems and structures designed to achieve the objectives of an organisation. Without systems and structures, there are no guiding principles to ensure harmonious completion of task as maybe scheduled.

Summary and Conclusion:

Respondents identified eight critical contributions of leadership as follows: developing vision and setting direction for organisational progress, collaboration through trust, inspiration and innovation, providing greater opportunity for initiative and creativity, using influence as major incentive for higher performance, providing greater opportunity for grooming and learning, demonstrating genuine care for human wellbeing, and building harmonious and agile organisation. The eight critical contributions of management were identified as provision of relevant manpower skill and materials resources, developing annual objectives and strategy, greater opportunity for a continuous professional development, developing code of ethics for harmonious organisation, effective supervision of workforce and resources, effective supervision of implementation of policies and strategies, using reward system to induce higher productivity and establishing appraisal systems to measure performance. Majority of respondents indicated that to achieve organisational effectiveness, it is necessary to combine both leaderships and management functions and to do that a proportion of each was needed. Businesses depending on their modus operadi and business environment can exploit the advantages of the critical contribution of leadership and management functions for organisational performance and effectiveness. An equal proportion of both leadership and management are needed in organisational effectiveness.

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